

Trends in the Reactivity of Molecular O₂ with Copper clusters. Influence of Size and Shape.

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ABSTRACT. The adsorption and dissociation of molecular O₂ on copper clusters of varying size and morphology (Cu_n with n=3-8, 13, and 38 atoms) has been systematically investigated using several DFT approaches. Different modes of adsorption of molecular O₂ are found for each atomicity of the copper clusters, with their relative stability depending on the cluster morphology: *bridge* conformations are stabilized on planar clusters, while hollow *h-100* and *h-111* modes are preferentially formed on 3D clusters. O₂ adsorption energies correlate with the HOMO energy of the isolated copper clusters, but not with their atomicity. On the other hand, the degree of activation of the O-O bond, and therefore the activation energy barrier necessary to break it, depends on the charge transferred to the π* MO of O₂, which in turn is determined by the mode of adsorption of O₂ on the metal. Cluster morphology appears then as the key factor determining the catalytic activity of copper, since the most activating *h-111* and *h-100* adsorption modes leading to lower barriers are preferentially stabilized on 3D clusters, no matter their size. All computational levels considered, including periodic and molecular calculations, lead to similar trends and conclusions.

KEYWORDS. DFT, mechanism, Cu, activation, cluster

Introduction

Transition metal nanoparticles with diameter between 1 and 5 nm have become an increasingly interesting topic during the last two decades because of their improved catalytic properties with respect to those of bulk metals. Recent advances in controlled synthesis procedures and characterization techniques have allowed to identify subnanometric clusters, that is, aggregates composed by just a few atoms, as the catalytically active species in some relevant reactions like CO oxidation,¹ oxygen reduction reaction,² propane dehydrogenation,³ hydration of alkynes,⁴ olefin hydrogenation,⁵ and selective oxidation of alkanes, alkenes, alcohols or thiols.⁶⁻⁹

The controlled synthesis, stabilization and characterization of such small clusters is not an easy task, and relevant information about the origin of their exceptional catalytic activity has been obtained from extensive theoretical investigation of their geometric, electronic and chemical properties.^{3, 7, 9-15} Quantum chemical studies have demonstrated that the accessibility and low coordination of all atoms in the clusters, together with a molecular-like electronic structure consisting of discrete electronic levels, are key to understand the catalytic behavior of these entities.

Copper nanoparticles are good catalysts for important industrial processes such as alcohol synthesis,^{16, 17} water gas shift,¹⁸ deoxygenation of biomass-derived molecules,¹⁹ selective alkyne hydrogenation,²⁰ or CO electroreduction to liquid fuels,²¹ and in some of these reactions, in particular in the case of selective hydrogenations, the catalytic activity has been specifically attributed to small copper clusters.²² For this reason, copper clusters are currently a hot subject of research,^{23, 24} and several quantum chemical studies concerning the structure and electronic

properties of small copper clusters, in some cases combined with photoelectron spectroscopy measurements, can be found in the literature.²⁵⁻²⁹

The reactivity of copper clusters, and its evolution with the number of atoms in the cluster, has been less investigated. The interaction of CO and O₂ with Cu_n clusters with $n \leq 10$ atoms and the dissociative chemisorption of H₂ on Cu_n clusters of up to 15 atoms have been explored in detail, and a higher reactivity of copper clusters with an odd number of atoms has been reported with few exceptions.³⁰⁻³⁶ As regards mechanistic studies, only the dissociation of H₂O on Cu₇³⁷ and the mechanism of CO oxidation on Cu₆ and Cu₇ clusters³⁸ have been reported in the literature. We present now a systematic theoretical study of O₂ adsorption and dissociation on Cu_n clusters with $n=3-8, 13,$ and 38 atoms, this last model being considered here the size limit between clusters and nanoparticles. Different modes of adsorption of molecular O₂ have been considered for each atomicity of the copper clusters, and the transition states for dissociation of the O-O bond have been calculated with the objective of finding a trend with particle size in the reactivity of copper clusters.

There is, however, a methodological issue in the systematic study of metal clusters of increasing size, which is mainly related to the scaling of the computational cost with the number of electrons in the system. Density functional theory (DFT)^{39, 40} based methods are usually chosen because they provide reasonable accuracy at a relatively moderate computational cost. However, the cost of a DFT calculation based on atom-centered Gaussian orbitals scales with N^3 , being N the number of functions in the basis set.⁴¹⁻⁴³ This means that even using effective core potentials (ECP) to account for the core electrons of transition metals instead of an all-electron basis set, a limit will be eventually reached from which increasing the system size further is impractical. A different approach consists of performing periodic calculations in which the isolated clusters or

nanoparticles are placed in a unit cell that is periodically repeated in the three dimensions of space, and that employ plane wave basis sets within a reciprocal space representation that lead to a reduction in the computational scaling to N^2 or even N .⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ A key advantage of this approach is that small, intermediate size and large transition metal clusters or nanoparticles, as well as the upper size limit represented by extended surfaces, can be studied using a single methodology.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ However, since this method was initially conceived for solids, its accuracy when describing molecular systems might be less than that of DFT methods using atom-centered functions as basis sets. On the other hand, it is not clear whether the results obtained employing both methodological approaches can be directly compared without any other consideration. For this reason, the adsorption and dissociation of molecular O_2 on copper clusters of increasing size has been now investigated using both atom-centered Gaussian-type orbitals in molecular calculations and plane-wave basis sets in periodic calculations, and the results are compared in order to assess the reliability of the latter method when applied to small and intermediate size clusters and, in general, to provide a methodological reference for future calculations on transition metal systems.

Theoretical Methods and Models

All calculations in this work are based on density functional theory (DFT). Molecular calculations based on atom-centered Gaussian orbitals were performed using the Gaussian 09 program package⁵⁰, while the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP)^{45,51} was employed for periodic calculations with plane-wave basis sets. In addition, the MOLDEN⁵² and ChemCraft⁵³ programs were used throughout the work to visualize the systems and their frequencies, and to obtain a graphical representation of their molecular orbitals, respectively.

The functional by Perdew and Wang within the gradient corrected approach (GGA) was chosen to perform the computational study.⁵⁴ Periodic calculations were carried out with the PW91 exchange-correlation functional as implemented in the VASP code, and are labelled as p-PW91 throughout the manuscript.⁵⁵ In molecular calculations using the Gaussian software, the equivalent approach consists of combining the PW91 correlation functional with the B88 exchange functional by Becke,⁵⁶ and is labelled as BPW91. However, hybrid functionals that include a certain amount of the exact Hartree-Fock exchange are usually chosen due to their superior performance and improved accuracy.^{42, 43} For this reason, the Becke's hybrid three-parameter exchange functional⁵⁷ in combination with the PW91 correlation functional was also used in the present study, and the method is labelled as B3PW91.

In the case of molecular calculations using atom-centered Gaussian orbitals, it is crucial to correctly simulate the system behavior to select a sufficiently large basis set. In this work, the standard 6-311+G(d,p) basis set by Pople was always used for oxygen atoms.⁵⁸ For Cu atoms, the all-electron triple zeta (TZ) 6-311+G(d,p) Wachters-Hay basis set,^{59, 60} with added polarized and diffuse functions, was selected as reference for benchmark calculations with other less expensive basis sets, namely the LANL2DZ and the Def2TZVP sets. The LANL2DZ basis set combines Los Alamos effective core potential with a double zeta (DZ) set for valence electrons, and it is widely used for transition metals due to its low computational cost.^{61, 62} The Def2TZVP basis set constitutes a relatively recent reformulation of the split-valence triple zeta basis set (TZVP) from Ahlrichs and co-workers, and it has been reported to be close to the basis set limit for DFT calculations.^{63, 64} A comparative study of the three basis sets was performed using the hybrid B3PW91 functional, and the data obtained are labelled as B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p), B3PW91/LANL2DZ and B3PW91/ Def2TZVP, respectively, throughout the manuscript.

In the periodic calculations using the VASP code, the valence density was expanded in a plane wave basis set with a kinetic energy cutoff of 450 eV, and the effect of the core electrons in the valence density was taken into account by means of the projected augmented wave (PAW) formalism.⁴⁴ The copper clusters and O₂ molecules were placed in a 20x20x20 Å³ cubic box, large enough to avoid spurious interactions between periodically repeated clusters or adsorbates, and integration in the reciprocal space was carried out at the Γ k-point of the Brillouin zone.

In all cases, the positions of all atoms in the system were fully optimized without any restriction, and all stationary points were characterized by pertinent frequency analysis calculations. When using the Gaussian code, transition states were determined through potential energy surface (PES) scans along with the subsequent optimizations and vibrational frequency calculations. When using the VASP code, transition states were located using the DIMER algorithm,^{65, 66} and vibrational frequencies were calculated numerically.

As regards the treatment of spin, periodic calculations with VASP program were always spin polarized, while for molecular calculations using the Gaussian code the two lowest possible multiplicities for each system were considered. Atomic charges and molecular orbital distributions were calculated using the natural bond order (NBO) approach.⁶⁷ The Basis Set Superposition Error (BSSE) in molecular calculations was determined using the counterpoise method⁶⁸ and dispersion interactions were taken into account by means of the B97D functional.⁶⁹

Results and discussion

3.1. Isolated copper clusters. In general, different isomers with energies close to the ground state structures are usually found for metal clusters, especially as the particle size increases. The

equilibrium geometries of the lowest energy isomers of Cu_n clusters with $3 \leq n \leq 8$, and their relative stability at the different levels of calculation considered in this work are shown in Figure 1, together with the optimized structures of the cuboctahedral isomers of Cu_{13} and Cu_{38} , and a more stable irregular Cu_{13} system. The planar structure for Cu_7 was included to confirm the size at which copper clusters become preferentially three-dimensional, although it is not the third most stable structure for this atomicity. The lowest spin multiplicity, that is, singlet for even values of n and doublet for odd values of n , was found to be the most stable at each cluster size.

In agreement with previous studies,²⁵⁻²⁹ all methods indicate that planar (2D) isomers are the most stable up to $n = 6$, and three-dimensional (3D) structures are clearly preferred for clusters containing 7 or more atoms. For Cu_4 , Cu_6 and Cu_7 clusters, the difference in energy between the two most stable isomers for each atomicity does not depend on the theoretical method used, with calculated relative energies differing by less than 1,5 kcal/mol. In other cases, however, the influence of the computational level employed is non-negligible. Thus, for Cu_5 and Cu_6 , the difference in energy between the 2D and 3D isomers (notice that the second most stable isomer of Cu_6 , labelled $\text{Cu}_6.\text{star}$, is not absolutely planar, but it is composed by one layer of atoms and therefore cannot be considered 3D) is slightly larger when the hybrid B3PW91 functional is used, with the largest deviation being obtained with the less accurate LANL2DZ basis set. In the case of the Cu_8 cluster the order of stability of the two lowest energy isomers is reversed when some Hartree-Fock exchange is included in the hybrid functional, although the difference in stability between them is less than 3 kcal/mol in all cases. It is important to remark that the co-existence of both isomers is supported by experimental results by Lecoultre et al.²⁶, who showed that both isomers contribute to the measured UV-visible absorption spectra of Cu_8 . As regards

the difference between molecular and periodic calculations, the most remarkable result is the larger stabilization of the irregular Cu₁₃ structure at the p-PW91 level.

To compare optimized geometries, the average Cu-Cu distance in each cluster at the several computational levels considered in this work was plotted in Figure 2 against the same parameter obtained with the reference B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) method. In all cases, a linear relationship is clearly observed. While the best correlation is found at the B3PW91/Def2TZVP level, the slope is in turn best for the p-PW91 method ($R^2 = 0,992$ and $m=0,914$ versus $R^2=0,946$ and $m=1,007$; See table S1 of the Supporting Information for details). Non-hybrid methods yield systematically shorter Cu-Cu distances, a trend that is more pronounced in the case of periodic p-PW91 calculations. The only exception corresponds to the irregular Cu₁₃ cluster at the BPW91/Def2TZVP level, and is due to the fact that the optimized structure at this level is not exactly equivalent to those obtained with the other methods. It is important to remark that the average Cu-Cu distances are clearly shorter for planar clusters, and increase as systems become 3D.

3.2. O₂ adsorption and activation. Adsorption of molecular O₂ over copper clusters leads to several different types of complexes, depicted in Scheme 1. In the case of small planar clusters, O₂ interaction preferentially occurs at their edges and corners, and the possible adsorption modes are labeled as *mono*, when only one bond is formed between a O atom of molecular O₂ and a low coordinated Cu atom; *top*, when the two O atoms of molecular O₂ are directly attached to the same low coordinated Cu atom, and *bridge*, when each of the two O atoms in the molecule is directly attached to one Cu atom in the cluster. In the case of 3D copper clusters and nanoparticles, O₂ can also occupy hollow positions on the (111) and (100) facets, and the complexes obtained are labeled according to the facet where they adsorb: *h-111* or *h-100*. The

optimized structures of the most stable adsorption complexes formed by interaction of molecular O₂ with Cu_n copper clusters with n = 3-8 are depicted in Figure 3, and the most relevant parameters describing this interaction (adsorption energies, optimized O-O bond lengths, O-O vibrational frequencies and net charge transferred to O₂) computed at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level are summarized in Table 1. Adsorption energies E_{ads} are calculated as:

$$E_{\text{ads}} = E(\text{Cu}_n\text{-O}_2) - E(\text{O}_2) - E(\text{Cu}_n)$$

where E(Cu_n-O₂) is the total energy of the adsorption complex, E(O₂) is the total energy of an isolated O₂ molecule in the triplet state, and E(Cu_n) is the total energy of the most stable Cu_n isomer for each atomicity. The corresponding values obtained with the B3PW91/LANL2DZ, B3PW91/Def2TZVP, BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 methods are listed in Tables S2-S5 in the Supporting Information.

3.2.1. Adsorption complexes. In agreement with a previous study by Yuan et al.³⁴, the *bridge* conformation is the most stable for planar Cu₃, Cu₄ and Cu₅ clusters, (structures 1, 3, 7-9 in Figure 3), followed by *top* (structures 2 and 4) and *mono* modes (structures 5 and 10), and the interaction is stronger with the clusters having an odd number of electrons (Cu₃ and Cu₅). Thus, the calculated adsorption energies at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level are larger than -37 kcal mol⁻¹ for the most stable *bridge* conformers on Cu₃ and Cu₅, and significantly lower, -21 kcal mol⁻¹, for the *bridge* conformation on Cu₄ (see Table 1). When O₂ was initially placed above the planar Cu₄ cluster, geometry optimization without any restriction led to structure 6, which corresponds to O₂ adsorbed on a 111 facet of a tetrahedral Cu₄ cluster, adopting the *h-111* conformation depicted in Scheme 1. This complex is only 1,6 kcal mol⁻¹ less stable than structure 3. It was not possible however to optimize the geometry of the 3D Cu₄ cluster in the absence of

an adsorbed O₂ molecule, and all attempts finally ended in the most stable planar isomer shown in Figure 1. As mentioned in the computational details section, two spin states were initially considered for each adsorption complex. A doublet state was found to be the most stable for all structures obtained by adsorption of O₂ on planar Cu₃ and Cu₅, but in the case of Cu₄ a triplet state was found for O₂ adsorbed on the 2D cluster while structure 6 was obtained as singlet.

The interaction of molecular O₂ with the two bi-dimensional isomers of Cu₆ (structures 14-17 in Figure 3) is really weak, with calculated adsorption energies lower than -5 kcal mol⁻¹ (see Table 1). In these systems molecular O₂ adsorbs on low coordinated copper atoms of Cu₆ adopting a *mono* conformation, except in structure 15 in which a *bridge* complex is formed and a small deformation of the cluster geometry occurs. The most stable spin state for these four structures is triplet.

When 3D structures are considered for Cu₅ and Cu₆, the *h-III* adsorption mode is obtained, in which one O atom is directly attached to a copper atom and the other O atom is occupying a bridge position between two copper atoms (see structures 12 and 18 in Figure 3). The *h-III* complex is 3,5 kcal mol⁻¹ less stable than the *bridge* mode on Cu₅, and 5 kcal mol⁻¹ more stable than the *bridge* mode on Cu₆. Moreover, the formation of three Cu-O bonds in structure 18 modifies its electronic distribution and the most stable spin state is singlet, in agreement with Yuan et al.'s results.³⁴ As the atomicity of the clusters increases, the number of adsorption complexes with similar stability becomes larger, and the calculated adsorption energy values decrease. Thus, six different adsorption complexes with interaction energies ranging from -21 to -7 kcal mol⁻¹ are described for Cu₇ in this work (structures 22 to 27 in Figure 3), all of them doublet in nature. The most stable systems involve O₂ adsorbed in a *bridge* mode, either on top

of the cluster or at its edge, followed by a *h-111* conformer, and *mono* or *top* modes at different positions.

In the case of the Cu₈ cluster we initially considered the adsorption of O₂ at different positions on the two most stable Cu₈ isomers described before, whose co-existence has been experimentally demonstrated as already mentioned.²⁶ However, the formation of copper-oxygen bonds modifies the geometry of the metal clusters in such a way that it is not always possible to clearly identify the initial structure of the isolated Cu₈ cluster. Therefore, only six stable adsorption complexes with interaction energies ranging between -16 and -10 kcal mol⁻¹, some of them previously reported by Yuan et al,³⁴ are described in this work (structures 28 to 33 in Figure 3). In the most stable system obtained (structure 28), each of the two oxygen atoms in O₂ molecule is directly attached to two Cu atoms that are situated forming the square planar arrangement characteristic of the (100) facet, a mode that has been labeled as *h-100* in Scheme 1. Structure 29, with O₂ adsorbed on a (111) facet of the cluster, is less than 1 kcal mol⁻¹ higher in energy. The calculated adsorption energies obtained for structures 30 to 33, in which O₂ adopts either *h-111* or *bridge* conformations, differ by less than 2 kcal/mol (see Table 1), suggesting that several different adsorption geometries may co-exist on 3D copper clusters. It is important to remark that while the most stable spin state for all *bridge* conformers formed on Cu₈ is triplet, the *h-111* and *h-100* modes lead to a singlet spin state of the system.

In order to bring some light into the relative stability of the O₂ adsorption complexes described above, the electronic structure of copper clusters of different size and shape was analyzed in more detail. The interaction of molecular O₂ with transition metal clusters and nanoparticles involves a transfer of electron density from the metal to the anti-bonding π^* molecular orbital of O₂. Taking into account that the degree of electron density transfer depends on the difference in

stability and the spatial overlap between the orbitals involved, the composition and stability of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of the Cu_n clusters considered in this work are plotted in Figure 4. In all cases, the HOMO consists of several lobes fully accessible to interaction with reactant molecules. The strong interaction of O_2 with $\text{Cu}_3, \text{Cu}_5, \text{Cu}_5\text{-3D}, \text{Cu}_6\text{-3D}$ or Cu_{13} (see Table 6 for E_{ads} values on Cu_{13}) is related to the low stability and therefore better accessibility of the electrons in the HOMOs of these systems. In contrast, the extremely low reactivity of 2D Cu_6 clusters is due to the high stability of their corresponding HOMOs. Interestingly, O_2 adsorption on Cu_8 tends to modify the structure of the cluster towards the isomer with the higher E_{HOMO} to facilitate interaction. The direct relationship existing between the stability of the HOMO and the adsorption energy of the most stable complex found on each Cu_n cluster is clearly observed in Figure 5.

3.2.2. Activation of molecular O_2 . The electron density transfer from the HOMO of the metal to the anti-bonding π^* molecular orbital of O_2 , responsible for O_2 interaction with metals, causes a lengthening of the O-O bond distance and consequently a shift in the calculated ν_{OO} vibrational frequency. As described before for gold and silver,⁷⁰⁻⁷² the degree of charge transfer and activation of the O-O bond depends directly on the mode of adsorption, and not so much on the size of the metal clusters. Thus, when molecular O_2 adsorbs adopting a *mono* conformation, the amount of charge transferred from the copper cluster is always lower than -0,5 e. The optimized O-O distances are between 1,22 and 1,28 Å, and consequently the calculated stretching vibrational frequencies are usually larger than 1200 cm^{-1} . In the few structures corresponding to a *top* adsorption mode there is a charge transfer of -0,4 – -0,6 e, and consequently the optimized O-O distances are in the 1,29–1,32 Å range, and the ν_{OO} frequencies are around 1170 cm^{-1} . A similar degree of activation is found for O_2 molecules adsorbed in a *bridge* mode. Although the

degree of charge transferred is slightly larger (between -0,6 and -0,8 e), the optimized O-O bond lengths are within 1,31–1,33 Å, and the calculated stretching frequencies take values around 1160–1180 cm⁻¹. On the other hand, adsorption of molecular O₂ on the 100 and 111 facets of 3D clusters of any atomicity allows a charge transfer larger than -1,0 e that leads to a higher degree of molecular activation reflected in optimized O-O distances in the 1,41–1,52 Å range and calculated vibrational frequencies between 700 and 800 cm⁻¹.

Figure 6 clearly shows the direct relationship existing between charge transferred and activation of the O-O bond, and the key role of the mode of adsorption of O₂ on this activation. The correlation between the net charge on O₂ after adsorption and the increase in the r_{OO} bond lengths with respect to the gas phase value is almost linear (see Figure 6, top). The black lines corresponding to *mono* conformations lie in the right bottom part of the plot, while the largest qO₂ and Δr_{OO} values are found for the red square and green triangles describing the *h-100* and *h-111* adsorption modes respectively. In a similar way, the large increase in the r_{OO} bond lengths found for *h-100* and *h-111* adsorption modes leads to shifts of more than 800 cm⁻¹ in the calculated ν_{OO} vibrational frequencies. On the contrary, no clear trend was found for adsorption energies when they were plotted against the charge transferred (see Figure S1 in the Supporting Information).

3.2.3. Comparison of methods. In order to provide a methodological reference for theoretical studies on transition metal clusters, the adsorption and activation of O₂ on copper clusters of increasing size was also calculated using computationally cheaper methods. The same structures with the same order of stability are obtained at the other computational levels considered (see Table 2). The only exceptions are the three lowest energy isomers of O₂ adsorbed on Cu₇ cluster, whose relative stability order changes when non-hybrid functionals are used (22 > 24 > 23 at the

BPW91/def2tzvp level, and $22 > 24 > 23$ at the p-PW91 level), and four isomers of O₂ adsorbed on Cu₈ (structures 30 to 33) whose stability differs by less than 2 kcal mol⁻¹ and their relative ordering can therefore easily change with the methodology employed.

As mentioned before, the most relevant parameters describing the interaction of O₂ with Cu_n clusters obtained at the B3PW91/LANL2DZ, B3PW91/Def2TZVP, BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 levels are listed in Tables S2-S5 in the Supporting Information. To facilitate the comparative analysis of results, the adsorption energy E_{ads}, net charge transferred qO₂, increase in the OO bond length Δr_{OO} and shift in the ν_{OO} vibrational frequency values provided by the different computational levels considered are plotted in Figure S2 against the same parameters obtained with the reference B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) method. The slopes, ordinate at the origin, and correlation coefficients for all regression lines are summarized in Table S6 in the Supporting Information.

In the case of adsorption energies, a linear relationship is clearly observed for all computational levels, with the best correlation being found for the B3PW91/Def2TZVP method ($r^2 = 0,998$). Non-hybrid methods yield systematically larger adsorption energies, this trend being more pronounced in the case of periodic p-PW91 calculations with a deviation of -13 kcal mol⁻¹ (see Figure S2). The different performance of hybrid and non-hybrid methods is more evident in the calculation of charge distributions. The correlation coefficients R^2 for BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 levels are not so good, 0,97 and 0,96, respectively, and the slopes of the regression lines are less than unity, 0,84 and 0,72, respectively. This means that the degree of charge transfer is underestimated for small clusters and overestimated for the largest systems. The poorer behavior of non-hybrid methods is also observed in the optimized O-O distances and calculated vibrational frequencies. For these properties, the slope of the correlation line is always close to

unity, but the R^2 values for p-PW91 method are 0,93 for Δr_{OO} and 0,90 for Δv_{OO} (see Table S6 in the Supporting Information). In contrast, the overall performance of the hybrid B3PW91/Def2TZVP method is excellent in all cases.

Finally, the effect of including Zero-Point Vibrational Energies (ZPVE) and correcting for the Basis Set Superposition Error (BSSE) has been checked at the B3PW91/Def2-TZVP level, and the results are summarized in Table S7 in the Supporting Information. Both corrections are destabilizing, and take values between 0,2 and 1,2 kcal mol⁻¹ in the case of ZPVE and are slightly larger for BSSE corrections, in the 1,2 – 2,8 kcal mol⁻¹ range except for one largest value of 3,4 kcal mol⁻¹. The order of stability of the structures investigated is not altered by these corrections, except again for the four isomers of O₂ adsorbed on Cu₈ whose relative stability differs by less than 2 kcal mol⁻¹. The influence of dispersion interactions was taken into account by using the B97D functional as implemented in the Gaussian09 software and, again, the difference between the B97D and B3PW91 calculated adsorption energies is in most cases less than 2 kcal mol⁻¹, except for the molecules adsorbed in a *mono* conformation that are stabilized by around 4 kcal mol⁻¹ (see Table S7 in the Supporting Information.)

3.3. O₂ dissociation. The first elementary step in the mechanism of metal-catalyzed oxidation reactions is usually the dissociation of the O-O bond of molecular O₂ yielding two O atoms adsorbed on the metal surface. This elementary step has been now systematically investigated over Cu_n clusters of increasing size. Taking as starting point the most stable O₂ adsorption complex found for each atomicity of the copper cluster (with few exceptions described below), the transition state for the dissociation of the O-O bond and the reaction product consisting of two O atoms adsorbed on the cluster have been optimized, and their nature characterized by means of frequency calculations. Given the large adsorption energies obtained for O₂ complexes

on 3D Cu₅ and Cu₆ clusters, dissociation on these isomers has also been considered. Following the same reasoning, the study on 2D Cu₆ clusters was discarded due to the very low adsorption energies found for them. It is important to mention at this point that, although the *bridge* conformers 11 and 22 were initially taken as starting point for O₂ dissociation over 3D Cu₅ and Cu₇ clusters, calculations always led to dissociation paths involving structures 12 and 24, where the O₂ molecule is adsorbed in a *h-111* mode. This is justified by the larger activation of O₂ molecule when adsorbed in such mode, and by the relative low difference in energy between the *bridge* and *h-111* conformers. So, the reaction paths starting from *h-111* structures are described below for 3D Cu₅ and Cu₇ clusters. The optimized structures of reactant (R), transition state (TS), and product (P) for each process are depicted in Figure 7, and the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) calculated adsorption (E_{ads}), activation (E_{act}) and reaction (ΔE) energies, together with the optimized values of the O-O distance in the TS are summarized in Table 3. Activation (E_{act}) and reaction (ΔE) energies are calculated as:

$$E_{\text{act}} = E(\text{TS}) - E(\text{R})$$

$$\Delta E = E(\text{P}) - E(\text{R})$$

where E(R), E(TS) and E(P) are the total energies of the reactant (R), transition state (TS), and product (P) for each process. The corresponding values obtained at the less computationally demanding B3PW91/LANL2DZ, B3PW91/Def2TZVP, BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 levels are summarized in Tables S8-S11 in the Supporting Information.

3.3.1. Reaction mechanism. Dissociation of molecular O₂ over planar Cu₃ and Cu₄ clusters follows a pathway similar to that previously described for small gold and silver clusters.^{15, 72} Starting from O₂ adsorbed in a *bridge* conformation, the rupture of the O-O bond occurs via

transition state structures (34 and 37 in Figure 7) in which only one of the O atoms can be stabilized through formation of new Cu-O bonds. As a consequence, the calculated activation energies are really high, 54,2 and 39,3 kcal mol⁻¹ for Cu₃ and Cu₄ clusters, respectively. After dissociation, however, the two O atoms occupy bridge positions between two copper atoms, so that both processes are clearly exothermic. It is important to remark that the optimized geometry of the reaction product P over a Cu₃ cluster varies with the computational method used. Thus, while the hybrid B3PW91 functional yields structure 35 in which one of the three Cu-Cu bonds initially present in the cluster is broken, with the non-hybrid BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 methods structure 36 containing three similar Cu-Cu bonds is obtained.

Two different initial reactant structures were considered to investigate the dissociation of O₂ over clusters containing five copper atoms, the *bridge* conformer 7 over planar Cu₅, which is the most stable adsorption complex found for this atomicity, and the *h-III* conformer 12 over Cu₅-3D cluster, with the highest degree of molecular O₂ activation. In the transition state obtained over planar Cu₅ (structure 39 in Figure 7), one of the O atoms is in the cluster plane forming a bridge between two copper atoms, while the other O atom is placed on the cluster forming three new Cu-O bonds. However, this situation is not stable and the calculated activation energy is really high, 40,8 kcal mol⁻¹. Moreover, the process involves important structural changes in the Cu₅ cluster that, in the product structure 40, has evolved to a 3D system. The global process is clearly exothermic, suggesting that planar Cu₅ clusters might be converted to 3D structures by reaction with O₂, although a high activation barrier should be overcome. Another pathway involves structure 12, which is 18,2 kcal mol⁻¹ less stable than structure 7, as initial reactant R. As described before, this *h-III* adsorption mode facilitates the charge transfer necessary to activate the O-O bond. As a consequence, the optimized r_{OO} distance in structure 12 is already 1,467 Å,

and increases to 2,004 Å in the transition state structure 41. The calculated activation energy for this pathway is only 14,8 kcal mol⁻¹ and the process is again highly exothermic.

As previously mentioned, 2D Cu₆ clusters interact weakly with O₂ and are not able to efficiently activate the O-O bond, and therefore we studied the dissociation of O₂ over the 3D Cu₆ isomer, starting from the most stable structure 18 in which O₂ molecule is adsorbed on the 111 facet. The geometry of the transition state (structure 43) is similar to that found over Cu₅-3D (structure 41). The optimized O-O distance is 2,0 Å, and the disposition of the O atoms is equivalent, with both of them sharing one low coordinated copper atom and being stabilized via formation of two other Cu-O bonds. Accordingly, the calculated activation energy is nearly the same, 14,9 kcal mol⁻¹. Further increase of cluster atomicity does not significantly change the reaction pathway described for 3D Cu₅ and Cu₆ clusters. The geometry of the transition state obtained for O₂ dissociation over Cu₇ cluster (structure 45) is equivalent to those previously described, and the calculated activation energy is only slightly higher, 17,7 kcal mol⁻¹. In the most stable adsorption complex found over Cu₈ cluster, O₂ is adsorbed over a 100 facet, with each oxygen atom forming two bonds with two copper atoms. The number of Cu-O bonds present in the system does not change in the transition state 47, and the reaction coordinate is only associated to the elongation of the O-O bond and to some deformation of the cluster geometry. Again, the calculated activation barrier is low, 15,2 kcal mol⁻¹.

3.3.2. Role of cluster morphology in O₂ dissociation. These results suggest that it is not cluster atomicity but cluster morphology the main parameter determining the catalytic activity of copper towards O₂ dissociation, a proposal that is clearly confirmed by comparing the two energy profiles obtained over 2D and 3D Cu₅ clusters with those calculated over the planar Cu₄ and the 3D Cu₆ Cu₇ and Cu₈ systems in Figure 8. The four energy profiles corresponding to 3D clusters

are similar, and involve activation barriers significantly lower than those found over planar clusters, regardless the stability of the initial adsorption complex formed. It is also important to remark that the mode of adsorption of the reactant R is also different on 2D and 3D clusters. Thus, *bridge* conformations are found over planar Cu₄ and Cu₅ clusters, while *h-III* modes, which lead to a higher degree of molecular activation, are usually found over 3D clusters.

To gain insight into the influence of cluster morphology and mode of adsorption on the reactivity of copper clusters, the complete reaction path for dissociation of an O₂ molecule over a 3D Cu₄ cluster (structure 6) and adsorbed in a *h-III* mode over a Cu₃ cluster (structure 53 in Figure 9b) have been calculated, and the energy profiles and structures involved are plotted in Figure 9. The reaction mechanism over a 3D Cu₄ cluster is not completely equivalent to those previously described, and involves two consecutive elementary steps with very low activation energies. In the transition state for the first step (structure 49 in Figure 9a), the O-O bond length increases to 1,56 Å while the 3D Cu₄ cluster flattens. An IRC calculation from this transition state 49 leads to intermediate species 50, in which the O₂ molecule is not dissociated but inserted into the cluster, with an optimized O-O distance of 1,56 Å. Then, through transition state 51 that resembles those found over Cu₅, Cu₆ and Cu₇ 3D clusters, the O-O bond is finally broken and species 52, with two O atoms adsorbed on a planar Cu₄ cluster, is obtained. The activation energy for this pathway is only 9,1 kcal mol⁻¹, and the process is clearly exothermic. It should be mentioned at this point that all species involved in the mechanism are singlet, except for the reaction product 52 that is more stable in the triplet state. Therefore, the reaction energy ΔE for the global process is -29,7 kcal mol⁻¹ considering the singlet state for structure 52 and -39,0 kcal mol⁻¹ considering the most stable triplet state.

Going one step further, the dissociation of O₂ adsorbed in a *h-111* conformation over the smallest system exposing a 111 facet, that is, the Cu₃ cluster, was theoretically investigated. In structure 53 (Figure 9b), like in other *h-111* adsorption complexes, the large amount of charge transferred to O₂ (-1,325 e⁻), causes a high degree of activation of the O-O bond, reflected in a long r_{OO} value and a calculated ν_{OO} vibrational frequency of 749 cm⁻¹. In the transition state 54 the O-O bond lengthens to 1,876 Å, and the geometry of the whole system resembles that of the transition states previously described for 3D Cu₅, Cu₆ and Cu₇ clusters (structures 41, 43 and 45 in Figure 7). From this transition state, structure 35 with the two O atoms forming symmetrical bridges between two Cu atoms is obtained in a highly exothermic process. Since O₂ in adsorption complex 53 is already highly activated, the energy barrier for its dissociation is really low, only 7,6 kcal mol⁻¹, suggesting the possibility to dissociate the O-O bond through this pathway. However, although the adsorption of O₂ on Cu₃ in a *h-111* mode is exothermic with an adsorption energy value of -6,8 kcal mol⁻¹, the stability of this conformer is considerably lower than that of the *bridge* conformer 1, as depicted in Figure 9b. Considering the possibility that the most stable conformer 1 could evolve to the *h-111* mode and then follow the pathway through transition state 54 instead of via 34, the global activation barrier for the process would be still very high, 39,2 kcal mol⁻¹.

It can then be concluded from this part of the study that adsorption of O₂ in a *h-111* or *h-100* modes leads to higher activation of the O-O bond and, as a consequence, to lower activation energy barriers for its dissociation. It is also found that 3D clusters preferentially stabilize the more activating *h-111* and *h-100* modes, in contrast to 2D isomers that prefer *bridge* conformations. Altogether, this results in an enhanced reactivity for 3D clusters, but it also implies a higher stability against oxidation of small 2D copper clusters.

3.3.3. Comparison of methods. The performance of the computationally less demanding B3PW91/LANL2DZ, B3PW91/Def2TZVP, BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 methods in reactivity studies has been addressed by comparing the activation and reaction energies for O₂ dissociation obtained with these methods and summarized in Tables S8-S11 in the Supporting Information with those reported in Table 3 at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p). The activation E_{act} and reaction energies ΔE provided by the computationally cheaper methods listed above are summarized in Tables 4 and 5, and are plotted against the same parameter obtained with the reference B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) method in Figure S3 in the Supporting Information. The slopes, ordinate at the origin, and correlation coefficients for all regression lines are summarized in Table S12 in the Supporting Information. As discussed before in relation to O₂ adsorption and activation, the overall performance of the B3PW91/Def2TZVP method is excellent, with correlation coefficients of 0,999 for both activation and reaction energies, followed by B3PW91/LANL2DZ. Non-hybrid methods on the other hand yield systematically lower activation barriers and reaction energies. It has to be therefore concluded that it is not possible to directly compare results obtained with hybrid and non-hybrid functionals. However, taking into account the considerably lower computational cost of periodic p-PW91 calculations and its suitability to study larger clusters and nanoparticles, the trends in adsorption, activation and reaction energies with cluster size, at the five theoretical levels considered, are compared in Figure S4. It is important to remark that, despite the different energy values obtained with the different methods, their variation with increasing cluster size is almost equivalent. Thus, O₂ adsorption energies over planar Cu₃ and Cu₅ are systematically larger than over 3D systems, while activation and reaction energies for O₂ dissociation decrease with increasing cluster size.

3.3.4. O₂ dissociation over larger clusters and nanoparticles. Real catalysts usually consist of nanometric metal nanoparticles containing from tenths to hundreds of atoms, and can only be treated using periodic plane-wave based methods, like p-PW91. In order to extend this comparative study to more realistic systems, we have now included the two cuboctahedral M₁₃ and M₃₈ models previously used in our group to investigate the reactivity of gold and silver nanoparticles^{15, 70-72} as the largest systems that can be computationally treated with DFT methods based on atom-centered Gaussian orbitals. Based on previous theoretical studies on the size dependence of the reactivity of gold nanoparticles with 38, 55, 79, 116 and 147 atoms,⁷³ the differences in reactivity expected for systems larger than Cu₃₈ should be less important than those found in the subnanometric regime.

Both the *h-100* and *h-111* adsorption modes were considered on the Cu₁₃ and Cu₃₈ models. The energy profile over Cu₁₃ was obtained at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p), B3PW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 levels, but for computational reasons geometry optimizations on the Cu₃₈ nanoparticle were only performed at the p-PW91 level, and single point calculations at the B3PW91/Def2TZVP level were carried out on the p-PW91 optimized geometries for comparison. The optimized structures of reactants R, transition states TS and products P are depicted in Figure 10, and Table 6 summarizes the calculated adsorption, activation and reaction energies.

O₂ adsorption over Cu₁₃ cluster is always highly exothermic, with the p-PW91 adsorption energy values being systematically larger than the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) ones by ~ -14 kcal mol⁻¹, the same deviation previously found for the Cu_n clusters with n = 3-8. The optimized geometry of O₂ adsorbed in a *h-111* mode is not exactly equivalent at all theoretical levels discussed. Structure 55 in Figure 10 with one oxygen atom on top of a copper atom is obtained with the p-PW91

method, while the hybrid methods yield structure 56 with the two oxygen atoms occupying bridge positions between two copper atoms. O₂ dissociation occurs through transition state 57 with an activation energy of 13,8, 14,7 and 4,1 kcal mol⁻¹ at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p), B3PW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 levels, respectively, and the process is exothermic by ~ -80 kcal mol⁻¹. When O₂ adsorbs on a 100 facet of the Cu₁₃ cluster the degree of molecular activation is higher, and consequently the calculated activation energy for dissociation of the O-O bond is lower, around 9 kcal mol⁻¹ with the hybrid B3PW91 methods and only 0,8 kcal mol⁻¹ at the p-PW91 level. It is important to remark that structure 60 is not a true stationary point on the B3PW91 potential energy surfaces, and could only be obtained in an approximate way by stopping the geometry optimizations that finally converged to transition state 63. Two imaginary frequencies were obtained for structure 60 at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level, one of -815 cm⁻¹ associated to rupture of the O-O bond, and another one of only -16 cm⁻¹ associated to cluster deformation. This small value justifies the characterization of structure 60 as the transition state for O-O dissociation over a cuboctahedral Cu₁₃ cluster in order to compare with the corresponding p-PW91 pathway. On the other hand, only one imaginary frequency of -792 cm⁻¹ associated to O-O rupture was obtained for the structure 63 that connects adsorption complex 62 with structure 64. These species are involved in a reaction path that starts with O₂ adsorbed in the same *h-100* conformation over a distorted Cu₁₃ cluster. The process in this case requires an activation barrier of ~ 6 kcal mol⁻¹ at the B3PW91 levels and only 1,8 kcal mol⁻¹ at the p-PW91 level. Notice that, as discussed before for Cu_n clusters with n = 3-8, activation energies at the p-PW91 level are systematically lower than those provided by hybrid methods, although the difference between the computed E_{act} values seems to decrease as particle size increases.

Finally, O₂ dissociation over a cuboctahedral Cu₃₈ nanoparticle was explored at the p-PW91 level, and single point calculations with the B3PW91/Def2TZVP method were performed on the p-PW91 optimized geometries. The *h-111* and *h-100* adsorption complexes and the corresponding transition states for O-O dissociation over Cu₃₈ are geometrically similar to those found over Cu₁₃. Adsorption and dissociation of O₂ are clearly exothermic, and the activation barriers involved are not high, 2-4 kcal mol⁻¹ at the p-PW91 level and slightly higher, 8-10 kcal mol⁻¹ at the B3PW91/Def2TZVP//p-PW91 level.

These results indicate that while periodic non-hybrid p-PW91 methods yield systematically larger adsorption energies and lower activation barriers for O₂ dissociation when compared to the reference B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) computational level, the structures involved in the reaction mechanisms and the trends found as particle size increases are similar, and therefore the same chemical conclusions can be obtained irrespectively of the methodology employed.

Finally, it is interesting to compare the results obtained here for copper clusters and nanoparticles with those previously reported for gold and silver analogous systems at the same p-PW91 computational level.^{15,70-72} The calculated activation barriers for O₂ dissociation on small planar clusters are extremely high in all cases (45,4 kcal mol⁻¹ on Au₃,¹⁵ 60,9 kcal mol⁻¹ on Ag₃,⁷² and 35,8 kcal mol⁻¹ on Cu₃), but the O atoms interact more strongly with copper than with the other metals, as indicated by reaction energies that are endothermic for Au₃ and Ag₃, (3,0 and 23,9 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively) and clearly exothermic for Cu₃ (-29,5 kcal mol⁻¹, see Table 2). As particle size increases the process becomes energetically accessible and thermodynamically favorable on all systems, but with remarkable differences between the three metals considered. The calculated adsorption energies on gold and silver clusters or nanoparticles composed by 13 or 38 atoms range from -18,3 to -23,6 kcal mol⁻¹, while they are larger than -50 kcal mol⁻¹ on

copper systems. The calculated activation energies for O₂ dissociation are lower than 10 kcal mol⁻¹ on Au₁₃ and Au₃₈, almost negligible on Cu₁₃ and Cu₃₈ (~2 kcal mol⁻¹, see Table 6) and as high as ~20 kcal mol⁻¹ on Ag₁₃ and Ag₃₈. Finally, the dissociation process is moderately exothermic on gold and silver systems, with reaction energies ranging from -12,5 to -42,3 kcal mol⁻¹, and it is extremely favorable on Cu₁₃ for instance with a calculated reaction energy of -64,4 kcal mol⁻¹. These results indicate that although copper is more active towards O₂ dissociation than the other two coinage metals previously studied, the oxidized copper systems are so stable that their activity in oxidation reactions might be hindered by the energy cost required to transfer the adsorbed oxygen atoms to reactant molecules.

4. Conclusions. The adsorption, activation and dissociation of molecular O₂ over Cu_n clusters with n = 3-8, 13 and 38 has been theoretically investigated using five different computational levels, and the trends with particle size, particle shape and molecular orbital distribution have been analyzed in detail. O₂ interaction with copper clusters, as with other metal clusters, involves a transfer of electron density from the metal HOMO to the anti-bonding π* of O₂. The calculated adsorption energies over copper clusters of increasing atomicity and varying morphology clearly correlate with the HOMO energy of the isolated cluster. The electron density transfer resulting from this interaction activates and weakens the O-O bond, facilitating its dissociation. The degree of O-O bond activation, indicated by the optimized r_{OO} distances or the shifts in the ν_{OO} vibrational frequencies, directly correlates with the net charge on adsorbed O₂, and is determined by the mode of adsorption of O₂ on the copper clusters. Thus, adsorption on 100 or 111 facets allows a larger degree of electron density transfer than adsorption at corners or edges adopting *bridge*, *mono* or *top* conformations. The role of particle morphology is key because it determines the preferential mode of adsorption of O₂, with the most activating *h-100* and *h-111* modes being

preferentially stabilized over 3D clusters. The influence of particle size is partly related to particle shape. Small Cu_3 , Cu_4 and Cu_5 clusters are planar, and the activation energies necessary to dissociate O_2 are larger than 40 kcal mol^{-1} . Activation barriers around $\sim 15 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ are found for 3D clusters with $n = 5-8$, and still decrease to $6-10 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ over larger Cu_{13} or Cu_{38} nanoparticles. These results indicate that small planar 2D copper clusters are less active towards O_2 dissociation than larger 3D clusters or nanoparticles, but it also means that they should be more stable against oxidation, a feature that might be relevant when trying to stabilize metallic copper systems. On the other hand, the high stability of the oxidized 3D clusters and nanoparticles might have a negative impact into their reactivity in oxidation reactions, due to the energy cost required to transfer the adsorbed oxygen atoms to reactant molecules.

Careful comparison of the results provided by different computational levels, including periodic calculations with plane-wave basis sets and molecular calculations using atom-centered functions as basis sets show that the absolute values of adsorption, activation and reaction energies are not directly comparable. However, the species involved in the reaction mechanisms and the trends found with particle size and shape are similar, and allow to conclude that the barrier for O_2 dissociation decreases when the atomicity of the cluster increases.

Scheme 1. Modes of adsorption of O₂ on copper clusters.

Table 1. Calculated values at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory of the most relevant parameters describing the interaction of molecular O₂ with Cu_n (n = 3-6) clusters. Mode of adsorption, energy of adsorption (E_{ads}), O-O bond length (r_{OO}), O-O vibration frequency (ν_{OO}) and net charge transferred to O₂ (q_{O_2}). The corresponding optimized structures are depicted in Figure 3.

Cluster atomicity	Structure	Adsorption mode	E_{ads} (kcal mol ⁻¹)	r_{OO} (Å)	ν_{OO} (cm ⁻¹)	q_{O_2} (e ⁻)
Cu ₃	1	<i>bridge</i>	-38.4	1.323	1171	-0.684
	2	<i>top</i>	-29.0	1.320	1172	-0.564
Cu ₄	3	<i>bridge</i>	-21.2	1.326	1157	-0.673
	4	<i>top</i>	-13.9	1.291	1217	-0.385
	5	<i>mono</i>	-10.2	1.242	1317	-0.248
	6	<i>h-111</i>	-19.6	1.481	778	-1.283

Cu ₅	7	<i>bridge</i>	-37.2	1.330	1172	-0.692
	8	<i>bridge</i>	-24.0	1.331	1164	-0.765
	9	<i>bridge</i>	-13.1	1.316	1166	-0.644
	10	<i>mono</i>	-10.7	1.273	1213	-0.426
Cu ₅ -3D	11	<i>bridge</i>	-22.5 (-29.9) ^a	1.315	1183	-0.602
	12	<i>h-111</i>	-19.0 (-26.4) ^a	1.467	763	-1.210
	13	<i>top</i>	-15.1 (-22.5) ^a	1.310	1173	-0.460
Cu ₆	14	<i>mono</i>	-4.5	1.234	1383	-0.201
	15	<i>bridge</i>	-3.1	1.325	1158	-0.671
Cu ₆ -star	16	<i>mono</i>	-2.4 (-5.0) ^b	1.238	1353	-0.230
	17	<i>mono</i>	-0.8 (-3.4) ^b	1.219	1476	-0.056
Cu ₆ -3D	18	<i>h-111</i>	-22.7 (-30.7) ^a	1.479	779	-1.198
	19	<i>bridge</i>	-17.3 (-25.4) ^a	1.330	1172	-0.651
	20	<i>bridge</i>	-14.7 (-22.7) ^a	1.326	1168	-0.641
	21	<i>bridge</i>	-10.8 (-18.8) ^a	1.318	1161	-0.599
Cu ₇	22	<i>bridge</i>	-20.6	1.323	1180	-0.618
	23	<i>bridge</i>	-18.2	1.324	1185	-0.678
	24	<i>h-111</i>	-15.1	1.413	788	-0.958
	25	<i>mono</i>	-12.8	1.283	1167	-0.463
	26	<i>top</i>	-9.9	1.300	1172	-0.452
	27	<i>mono</i>	-6.8	1.254	1248	-0.333
Cu ₈	28	<i>h-100</i>	-16.3	1.521	720	-1.346
	29	<i>h-111</i>	-15.6	1.514	756	-1.241
	30	<i>h-111</i>	-11.9	1.487	784	-1.191
	31	<i>h-111</i>	-11.4	1.502	770	-1.218
	32	<i>bridge</i>	-11.1	1.320	1166	-0.641
	33	<i>bridge</i>	-10.3	1.318	1154	-0.634

^aThe values in parenthesis have been calculated with respect to the corresponding isolated Cu_n-3D isomer.

^bThe values in parenthesis have been calculated with respect to the isolated Cu₆-star isomer.

Table 2. Calculated values for the adsorption energy E_{ads}(in kcal mol⁻¹) of molecular O₂ on Cu_n (n = 3-8) clusters at the different computational levels of theory employed. The corresponding optimized structures are depicted in Figure 3.

Cluster	Structure	B3PW91/ 6-311+G(d,p)	B3PW91/ LANL2DZ	B3PW91/ Def2-TZVP	BPW91/ Def2-TZVP	p-PW91
Cu ₃	1	-38.4	-39.4	-38.6	-41.7	-50.9
	2	-29.0	-27.9	-28.8	-33.7	-41.9
Cu ₄	3	-21.2	-21.1	-20.9	-24.1	-32.5
	4	-13.9	-13.8	-13.8	-18.1	-24.1 ^d
	5	-10.2	-10.6	-9.9	-17.1	-20.5
	6	-19.6	-17.4	-19.3	-23.5	-30.6
Cu ₅	7	-37.2	-36.6	-36.6	-39.4	-49.4
	8	-24.0	-24.0	-23.7	-26.4	-34.7
	9	-13.1	-13.3	-12.9	-17.9	-26.2
	10	-10.7	-10.7	-10.3	-17.7	-24.5
Cu ₅ -3D	11	-22.5 (-29.9) ^a	- ^c	-23.0 (-30.0)	-27.5 (-32.6)	-34.1 (-40.4)
	12	-19.0 (-26.4)	- ^c	-18.7 (-25.8)	-25.2 (-30.4)	-33.2 (-39.5)
	13	-15.1 (-22.5)	-11.8 (-21.6)	-15.4 (-22.5)	-22.5 (-27.6)	-28.5 (-34.7)
Cu ₆	14	-4.5	-5.0	-4.4	-11.7	-17.4
	15	-3.1	-2.4	-2.9	-8.7	-17.1
Cu ₆ -star	16	-2.4 (-5.0) ^b	-2.3 (-5.8)	-2.4 (-5.0)	-10.2 (-12.6)	-15.1 (-18.2)
	17	-0.8 (-3.4)	-1.4 (-4.9)	-0.9 (-3.4)	-7.3 (-9.8)	-11.8 (-15.0)

Cu ₆ -3D	18	-22.7 (-30.7)	-19.6 (-30.6)	-22.8 (-30.2)	-29.4 (-34.2)	-33.2 (-39.8)
	19	-17.3 (-25.4)	-14.0 (-25.0)	-17.9 (-25.3)	-23.0 (-27.8)	-26.3 (-32.9) ^d
	20	-14.7 (-22.7)	-11.9 (-22.9)	-15.4 (-22.7)	-20.7 (-25.5)	- ^c
	21	-10.8 (-18.8)	-9.4 (-20.4)	-11.4 (-18.7)	-16.4 (-21.3)	- ^c
Cu ₇	22	-20.6	-21.6	-20.4	-22.8	-30.4
	23	-18.2	-17.5	-18.2	-20.6	-27.8
	24	-15.1	- ^c	-14.7	-21.4	-31.2
	25	-12.8	-13.6	-12.6	-18.3	-23.5
	26	-9.9	-9.5	-10.1	-15.9	-22.0
	27	-6.8	-7.3	-6.7	-14.1	-19.5
Cu ₈	28	-16.3	-14.8	-15.5	-18.2	-25.0
	29	-15.6	-12.7	-15.2	-21.5	-29.8
	30	-11.9	-9.0	-11.5	-18.1	-25.3
	31	-11.4	- ^c	-10.5	-16.3	-24.3
	32	-11.1	-10.0	-11.5	-16.6	-22.8
	33	-10.3	-9.8	-10.4	-16.5	-29.9

^aThe values in parenthesis have been calculated with respect to the corresponding isolated Cu_n-3D isomer.

^bThe values in parenthesis have been calculated with respect to the isolated Cu₆-star isomer.

^cStructure not found at this level of theory.

^dThe singlet state was found slightly more stable for this structure at this level, but the triplet state was kept to be consistent in the comparison between methods.

Table 3. Dissociation of O₂ over Cu_n (n = 3-8) clusters. Adsorption (E_{ads}), activation (E_{act}) and reaction (ΔE) energies calculated at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level of theory, together with the optimized values of the O-O distance in the TS. The corresponding optimized structures are depicted in Figure 8.

Cluster	E_{ads}	E_{act}	r_{OO} in TS	ΔE
atomicity	(kcal mol ⁻¹)	(kcal mol ⁻¹)	(Å)	(kcal mol ⁻¹)
Cu ₃	-38.4	54.2	2.123	-22.8
Cu ₄	-21.2	39.3	1.734	-30.4
Cu ₅	-37.2	40.8	1.849	-41.7
Cu ₅ -3D	-19.0 (-26.4) ^a	14.8	2.004	-54.1
Cu ₆ -3D	-22.7 (-30.7) ^a	14.9	2.020	-51.7
Cu ₇	-15.1	17.6	1.997	-58.2
Cu ₈	-16.3	15.2	2.172	-78.1

^aCalculated with respect to the corresponding isolated Cu_n-3D isomer.

Table 4. Calculated values for the activation energy E_{act} (in kcal mol⁻¹) corresponding to dissociation of molecular O₂ on Cu_n (n = 3-8) clusters at the different computational levels of theory employed. The corresponding optimized structures are depicted in Figure 8.

Cluster	B3PW91/ 6-311+G(d,p)	B3PW91/ LANL2DZ	B3PW91/ Def2-TZVP	BPW91/ Def2-TZVP	p-PW91
Cu ₃	54,2	64,7	56,0	38,1	35,8
Cu ₄	39,3	42,6	39,8	25,3	19,8 ^b
Cu ₅	40,8	44,9	41,3	32,2	30,8 ^c
Cu ₅ -3D	14,8	- ^a	15,5	6,4	6,2
Cu ₆ -3D	14,9	21,0	16,1	7,2	5,7
Cu ₇	17,6	- ^a	18,2	10,3	9,7
Cu ₈	15,2	22,4	16,3	1,7	1,0

^aReactants structure not found at this level of theory.

^bThe geometry of the TS (structure 37) is different and with a different spin (singlet) (see Figure S6).

^cThe geometry of the TS (structure 39) is different (see Figure S6).

Table 5. Calculated values for the reaction energy ΔE (in kcal mol⁻¹) corresponding to dissociation of molecular O₂ on Cu_n (n = 3-8) clusters at the different computational levels of theory employed. The corresponding optimized structures are depicted in Figure 8.

Cluster	B3PW91/ 6-311+G(d,p)	B3PW91/ LANL2DZ	B3PW91/ Def2-TZVP	BPW91/ Def2-TZVP	p-PW91
Cu ₃	-22,8	-9,0	-18,6	-25,7	-29,5 ^b
Cu ₄	-30,4	-18,3	-27,4	-35,8	-41,9
Cu ₅	-41,7	-34,2	-40,5	-43,2	-42,3
Cu ₅ -3D	-54,1	- ^a	-52,9	-53,9	-55,6
Cu ₆ -3D	-51,7	-44,6	-50,0	-49,4	-45,2 ^c
Cu ₇	-58,2	- ^a	-56,7	-57,2	-57,4
Cu ₈	-78,1	-69,2	-76,9	-79,8	-82,6 ^d

^aReactants structure not found at this level of theory.

^bThe geometry of the product (structure 36) is different (see Figure 8).

^cThe geometry of the product (structure 44) is different (see Figure S6).

^dThe geometry of the product (structure 48) is different (see Figure S6).

Table 6. Dissociation of O₂ over Cu₁₃ and Cu₃₈ clusters. Adsorption (E_{ads}), activation (E_{act}) and reaction (ΔE) energies calculated at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p), B3PW91/Def2TZVP (in parenthesis) and p-PW91 levels of theory. The corresponding optimized structures are depicted in Figure 10.

Cluster atomicity	Mode of adsorption	E _{ads} (kcal mol ⁻¹)		E _{act} (kcal mol ⁻¹)		ΔE (kcal mol ⁻¹)	
		B3PW91	p-PW91	B3PW91	p-PW91	B3PW91	p-PW91
Cu ₁₃	<i>h-111</i>	-45.6 (-45.9)	-62.5	13.8 (14.7)	4.1	-80.3 (-78.5)	-77.1
Cu ₁₃	<i>h-100</i>	-46.7 (-46.0)	-58.5	8.9 (9.4)	0.8	-74.6 (-74.1)	-77.8
Cu _{13-dis}	<i>h-100</i>	-48.5 (-47.4)	-64.0	6.0 (6.6)	1.8	-68.1 (-66.8)	-64.4
Cu ₃₈	<i>h-111</i>	(-23.7)	-39.7	(8.3) ^a	3.8	(-53.1) ^a	-50.1
Cu ₃₈	<i>h-100</i>	(-34.9)	-50.2	(10.3) ^a	2.4	(-40.3) ^a	-39.1

^aFrom B3PW91/Def2TZVP//p-PW91 single point calculations.

Figure 1. Optimized structures of the lowest energy isomers of Cu_n clusters with $n = 3-8, 13$ and 38, and relative energy (in kcal/mol) with respect to the most stable isomer for each atomicity at the different computational levels considered, from top to bottom: B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) (black), B3PW91/LANL2DZ (green), B3PW91/Def2TZVP (purple), BPW91/Def2TZVP (orange) and p-PW91 (blue).

Figure 2. Relationship between the average Cu-Cu distance (in Å) in Cu_n clusters of increasing size calculated at different theoretical levels and that obtained with the reference B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) method. B3PW91/LANL2DZ (green diamonds), B3PW91/Def2TZVP (purple squares), BPW91/Def2TZVP (orange circles) and p-PW91 (blue triangles) values are plotted. Empty symbols correspond to planar clusters, while full symbols are associated to three-dimensional isomers.

Figure 3. Structures for the adsorption of one O_2 molecule on the different copper clusters studied.

Figure 4. Stability and composition of the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) of Cu_n clusters with $n=3-8, 13$ calculated at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level. The optimized geometries of the copper clusters are also shown. E_{HOMO} in hartrees.

Figure 5. Relationship between adsorption energies of O_2 on copper clusters and the stability of the HOMO of the corresponding Cu_n cluster at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level.

Figure 6. Relationship between the bond length variation Δr_{OO} and the charge transferred q_{O_2} (top) and between the shift in the ν_{OO} vibrational frequency and the bond length variation Δr_{OO} (bottom) obtained at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level per adsorption mode: *mono* (black lines) *top* (blue circles) *bridge* (yellow diamonds) *h-111* (green triangles) and *h-100* (red squares).

Figure 7. Structures of reactants (R), transition states (TS) and products for the process of dissociation of one oxygen molecule by Cu_n clusters with $n = 3-8$.

Figure 8. Energy profiles for O₂ dissociation over Cu_n clusters with n = 4 (red), 5 (purple), 6 (dark blue), 7 (light blue) and 8 (green) at the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) level. Solid lines and dashed lines correspond to 2D and 3D clusters, respectively.

Figure 9. Energy profile (in blue) and structures involved in the dissociation of O₂ a) over a 3D Cu₄ cluster and b) adsorbed in a *h-III* conformation over a Cu₃ cluster. The optimized O-O bond lengths (in Å) are shown for each structure, and the B3PW91/6-311+G(d,p) calculated activation and reaction energies (in kcal mol⁻¹) are written beside the arrows. The energy profiles starting from bridge conformations over planar Cu₃ and Cu₄ clusters are included (in red) for comparison.

Figure 10. Structures of reactants (R), transition states (TS) and products (P) for the process of dissociation of one oxygen molecule by Cu_{13} and Cu_{38} clusters.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Tables summarizing adsorption, activation and reaction energies, and some relevant parameters describing O₂ activation computed at the B3PW91/LANL2DZ, B3PW91/Def2TZVP, BPW91/Def2TZVP and p-PW91 levels, and regression parameters for all regression lines plotted in the manuscript. Plot of adsorption energies versus charge transferred to O₂, energy profiles and some optimized structures. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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